

INTRODUCTION

The topic in question is relevant, since effective use of budget funds through procurement can contribute to developing local producers, creating jobs, and increasing tax revenues.

Public procurement is also important in solving social problems such as affordable housing, health care, and education. It helps stimulate innovation and supports startups and small businesses. In the context of global challenges, such as pandemics or economic crises, public procurement can become a tool for rapidly adapting the economy and social sphere to new conditions.

Thus, research on the potential of public procurement is important for understanding its role in economic and social development and making recommendations on how to improve its effectiveness.

Literature review

Corruption and fraud in public procurement are serious problems that negatively affect the economy, the quality of services, and citizens' trust in public institutions.

Thus, E. Carloni et al. believe that the problem of corruption in public procurement is pronounced, and its regulation requires close attention [1]. R. Coppier et al., using both analytical tools and numerical modeling, try to explain how effective economic policy is in reducing or eliminating "deviant behavior" in public procurement [2].

M. S. Lyra et al. note that fraudulent activities related to public procurement result in billions of euros in yearly losses. The authors from Brazil identified 22 firms with similar patterns of procurement activity, determined by their geographical location and field of activity. Creation of so-called profiles of organizations allows for highlighting those more susceptible to market manipulation and illegal actions [3].

B. C. Basheka writes that corruption in public procurement in Uganda involves abuse and deviation from established legal norms. The author notes, among other reasons, supplier collusion, supply of substandard goods and services, improper performance of construction works, etc. [4].

According to N. Dorasamy, the African procurement system is characterized by enormous corruption which played a large role in the continent's continuous regression in socio-economic development. The authors see the solution to this problem in strengthening various institutions of governance [5].

M. Siwandeti concludes that transparency and absence of corruption are the most important factors in suppliers' willingness to participate in the public e-procurement system [6].

Public procurement can serve as an economic and political tool, influencing various aspects of public life and governance.

J. M. Zabala-Iturriagagoitia focuses on public procurement as a policy tool that can promote regional innovation, entrepreneurship and growth, and transform the territory's industrial structure [7].

Thus, R. Caranta and P. C. Gomes write about how policy strategies that reduce information, market, and financial uncertainty shape small business innovation in China [8].

C. Wang et al. believe that the three problems in China's current public procurement policy are regulation of whole-process performance management needs to be optimized, of high-level performance management needs to be strengthened, and of whole-process performance disclosure needs to be improved [9].

B. K. O. Tas shows that better regulatory regimes for public procurement are associated with higher levels of competition and economic efficiency. Improved regulatory quality significantly increases the number of bidders and the likelihood that the procurement price will be lower than the perceived value [10].

I. A. Chagalima et al. write about the applicability of indirect suppliers in public procurement. According to the authors, public procurers may consider applying this practice in public organizations. However, caution should be exercised regarding the legal and regulatory structure that governs a country's public procurement system [11].

Digital technologies are increasingly important in public procurement, contributing to transparency, efficiency, and reduced corruption risks.

O. M. Pisareva et al. summarized the effective practices of implementing electronic public procurement systems in the European Union and the Russian Federation, identified critical factors of success in implementing technology and electronic procurement systems, as well as metrics for their evaluation, identified problem areas in forming public procurement platform, proposed solutions and recommendations to eliminate problem areas [12].

V. V. Borisova et al. consider the possibilities of using digital technologies and logistics tools in public procurement. They highlight the prerequisites and positive aspects of digital transformation and the associated risks. According to the authors, the electronic format of public procurement optimizes the costs accompanying trade operations and increases their efficiency by an average of 25-30% [13].

Based on the above, further in-depth analysis and understanding of how public procurement can influence economic and social development is necessary. Additional research aimed to identify effective mechanisms of control and transparency in procurement that would reduce corruption and increase citizens' trust in public institutions is relevant.

Research is needed to help allocate funds optimally through public procurement to maximize their contribution to economic growth and social development. It is also necessary to investigate approaches to addressing social problems (inequality, access to services, improving quality of life) through public procurement.

Thus, an integrated approach to research on the potential of public procurement that considers economic, social, environmental, and institutional aspects is needed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study's materials included articles on economics, management, and public procurement from periodicals *Decisions in Economics and Finance*, *Small Business Economics*, *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, *SN Business & Economics*, *Journal of Regulatory Economics*, *Future Business Journal*, and others. Books on economic development and social policy from the *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems* series were also used.

We used methods of comparative analysis of public procurement practices in different countries and regions. We assessed the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of public procurement.

STUDY RESULTS

Implementing public procurement is associated with various risks, including corruption.

In the analytical work of the National Research University 'Higher School of Economics' [14], the issue of public procurement risks is considered widely; the combination of four main criteria distinguishes different situations: cost-effectiveness of procurement – compliance of prices with market prices; competitiveness of procurement – possibility of access to procurement procedures for all interested parties and absence of preferences for one of them; quality and validity of procurement – compliance of purchased goods with the needs, both in the aspect of compliance of the terms of reference with the needs (validity) and in the element of compliance of the delivered goods with the requirements of procurement.

A. Konov et al. show that eight variants of a combination of these four criteria are the most common in Russia. The determining factors are the emphasis in the legislation on public procurement on competition and cost efficiency and the insufficient actual level of competitiveness development in various markets.

The authors further discuss the techniques that allow the contracting authority to manipulate procurement. They call such techniques “improper” because the purpose of manipulation is not always the corrupt benefit of the customer, but in some cases achievement of the required level by other criteria (most often by the criterion of the required quality of goods supplied), which due to the imperfection of procurement procedures (first of all, insufficiency of mechanisms to prevent unfair suppliers from winning in competitive procedures) is impossible without unique manipulation of them. The authors identify 100 main improper techniques, among which a separate subset is occupied by techniques aiming for corrupt purposes (similar to those considered in the methodological recommendations of the ONF). In addition, they believe in detailed situations where customers are forced to use manipulative techniques not for corruption purposes but to comply with other public procurement criteria, primarily to guarantee the delivery of goods of appropriate quality by a verified supplier. As a rule, this is achieved by secretly agreeing in advance with the desired supplier on such conditions of the tender, including the terms of reference and non-price selection criteria (staffing, experience in supplying similar goods, etc.), which guarantee its victory.

The problem, however, is that the formal illegality of such manipulative procedures, the need to build long-term informal ties with a pool of “trusted suppliers,” and the development of a loyal attitude to the techniques of manipulating the results of tenders facilitate using similar practices for corrupt purposes. In contrast, the entire formal preservation of the competitive procedure removes these purchases from the special attention of regulatory authorities.

In a situation with urgent procurement due to a threat to security or other national interests (for example, a pandemic of the new coronavirus infection or a special military operation in Ukraine), the balance of specific weights of importance of the above criteria of public procurement inevitably changes, as the need for a guaranteed supply of necessary goods comes to the fore. Notably, the criterion of competitiveness of public procurement identified by the experts aims not to achieve the goals of the current public procurement but to reach strategic economic objectives, such as developing a competitive environment. In fact, in case of a single public procurement, provided that prices and quality levels are equivalent, it does not matter whether it was a sole-source procurement or a competitive procedure, how broad the composition of the bidders was, and whether the client used manipulative techniques to determine the winner of the tender. However, all of the above affects the competitive environment and, consequently, the choice space in the situation of the following public procurement: in conditions of more developed competition, it is natural to expect lower prices, higher quality of goods, and increased innovative development. In normal conditions of economic activity, the idea to balance current objectives – to satisfy needs and to stimulate competitive environment – can be justified, but in case of urgent procurement, a clear priority

should be given to satisfying the needs of a particular public customer. The legislator, realizing this, at the beginning of the coronavirus pandemic, relaxed the rules on competition protection according to the new wording of Paragraph 4, Part 1 of Art. 93 of the Federal Law # 44 [15], “the purchase of goods, work or services for an amount not exceeding six hundred thousand rubles, or the purchase of goods for the amount provided for in Part 12 of this article, if such purchase is carried out in electronic form. At the same time, the annual volume of purchases that the customer is entitled to, based on this paragraph, shall not exceed two million rubles or exceed ten percent of the aggregate annual volume of the customer’s purchases and shall not be more than fifty million rubles”. In the previous version, the limits were 300,000 rubles for a single purchase from a single supplier and 5% of the annual procurement volume. The need to meet the needs of the SMO has led to a new relaxation of restrictions on procurement from a single supplier: removal of the total annual limit of RUR 50 million in case of procurement for the “implementation by the federal executive body responsible for the development and implementation of state policy in the field of defense, state agencies and state unitary enterprises subordinate to it, other federal executive bodies, the list of which is approved by the Russian Government.”

Thus, liberalization of procurement policy in emergency situations allows procurement from a single supplier quite legally, without resorting to manipulative procedures to ensure a pre-selected company winning the tender. On the other hand, the openness of the fact of choosing a single supplier deliberately marks this purchase as non-competitive, forcing one to look for other ways to control its validity, quality, and cost effectiveness. Such control methods can be divided into ex-ante and ex-post. Ex ante control (before selecting a supplier) should reduce the probability of choosing a known unreliable supplier prone to opportunism or not having the necessary competencies and resources to deliver the benefit. For this purpose, it is essential to develop business reputation standards and expand the practices of pre-qualification of suppliers, including considering the experience of several state-owned companies, such as Gazprom or Rosatom, where such mechanisms have long been used [16].

Ex-post control methods are necessary, first of all, in case of experimental or trust goods supply according to the Darby-Carney classification (see [9]). As known, procured goods under this classification fall into three main categories. Inspection goods are goods where quality can be verified before the purchase is made, for example, by taking samples in each batch to be purchased. They are the easiest to procure because the inspection can be done ex-ante, and if they do not meet the required level of quality, the purchase is rejected. Experimental goods are goods where conformity to the necessary level of quality can only be determined during operation. This may include most services and some technically complex goods, especially innovative ones. Trust goods are the most challenging category of goods to control and have

the highest degree of information asymmetry between supplier and customer: their quality cannot be fully assessed by the customer even after consumption. Fiduciary goods are more characteristic of private, non-public consumption, as individuals cannot have the necessary competencies to evaluate the number of services provided, works performed, etc. (e.g., in case of partially successful treatment, the patient cannot know whether the doctor did everything possible, whether the medical strategy was optimal, whether the costs incurred by the patient corresponded to objective needs, etc.). In public procurement, as a rule, the contracting authority must be competent to control the quality of the goods supplied, at least ex-post. Still, there may be exceptions due to the sudden need for the public contracting authority to perform functions not assigned to it (e.g., procurement of goods and services by various public entities to fight a pandemic). In turn, all three categories have two sub-options related to the presence/absence of external (expert) information on their quality in the market. Expert information about the quality of an inspection good (for example, in the form of a certificate of conformity in a voluntary certification system) excludes the need for the customer's control. In case of experimental and, especially, trust goods, involvement of external experts allows for a significant increase in the efficiency of quality assessment of procured goods and services.

Thus, methods of ex-post control used should include, first of all, the publicity of the conducted purchases and ensure the maximum possible expertise, including the analysis and generalization of end users of purchased goods, splitting the purchase into batches with stage-by-stage payment depending on the quality revealed during the operation of each previous batch of goods, stage of services, works (which allows using the mechanism of a single supplier, fitting into the price frame of a single purchase of up to 600 thousand rubles in the conditions of abolition of the price of goods, works, services, etc.). In turn, the information obtained from ex-post control of procurement should be accumulated in the state register of business reputation, replacing the unnecessarily narrowly applied register of unfair suppliers for subsequent ex-ante control in the next procurement. The application of life cycle contracts will allow the rise in the price limit of procurement from a single supplier, ensuring the quality of purchased complex, complex benefits having the nature of experimental or trust.

It should be taken into account that unique methods of analysis and control of procurement conducted in emergencies are desirable, as such situations may result in significant price instability of the markets, and the required speed of delivery of goods necessitates a price premium, so the comparison in the course of control and audit activities of prices for emergency purchases with planned ones may be incorrect. For this purpose, special codes are required marking emergency purchases for in-depth comparison only within this category, considering the markets' rapidly changing state.

This task can be facilitated by using modern information technologies and mathematical methods of big data processing, which allow identification of price anomalies in procurement through machine learning methods, pattern recognition, etc. However, these methods may not always lead to legally significant conclusions, so it is necessary to first accumulate initial experience of their use as a preliminary basis for subsequent checks, and then to identify the effectiveness of methods, their standardization, and subsequent implementation of conclusions at least of managerial and administrative nature.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the above, the following conclusion can be drawn: if, in normal economic and social conditions, regulation of public procurement aims for balance between the interests of a particular customer (acquisition of reasonable, quality goods at a reasonable price) and the interests of economic development as a whole (maintaining a competitive environment by stimulating competitive procedures of public procurement, encouraging the inclusion of small and medium-sized businesses, etc.), national security challenges demand balance of requirements and risks. In this regard, it is necessary to liberalize procurement from a single supplier further with the simultaneous development of methods to control its risks [17; 18].

Thus, public procurement, if properly organized, is a powerful tool to stimulate economic growth and promote social activity, for example, through support of small and medium-sized enterprises, as well as through introduction of social criteria into procurement (e.g., environmental and social standards) [19]. Improving public procurement can increase transparency and reduce corruption. This, in turn, can increase citizens' trust in public institutions and improve social stability. Increased interest in the topic of public procurement by researchers and practitioners can lead to new findings and recommendations that can help optimize its processes.

REFERENCES

1. Carloni, E., Polinori, P., & David, D. (2021). Public Procurement and Corruption: Perspectives, Rules, Experiences. In: Carloni, E., Gnaldis, M. (eds) Understanding and Fighting Corruption in Europe. Springer, Cham.
2. Coppier, R., Grassetti, F., & Michetti, E. (2021). Non-compliant behavior in public procurement: an evolutionary model with endogenous monitoring. *Decisions in*

- Economics and Finance*, 44, 459-483.
3. Lyra, M. S., Curado, A., Dam6sio, B. et al. (2021) Characterization of the firm-firm public procurement co-bidding network from the State of Cear6 (Brazil) municipalities. *Applied Network Science*, 6, 77.
 4. Basheka, B. C. (2021). Public Procurement Governance: Toward an Anticorruption Framework for Public Procurement in Uganda. In: Dorasamy, N., Fagbadebo, O. (eds) *Public Procurement, Corruption and the Crisis of Governance in Africa*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham
 5. Dorasamy, N. (2021). An Overview of Public Procurement, Corruption, and Governance in Africa. In: Dorasamy, N., Fagbadebo, O. (eds) *Public Procurement, Corruption and the Crisis of Governance in Africa*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
 6. Siwandeti, M., Sanga, C., Mfanga, A., & Panga, F. (2021). Vendors' Willingness Drivers for Participation in Public Electronic Procurement System, Ilala District, Tanzania. In: Mojekwu, J. N., Thwala, W., Aigbavboa, C., Atepor, L., Sackey, S. (eds) *Sustainable Education and Development*. Springer, Cham.
 7. Zabala-Iturriagagoitia, J. M. (2022). Fostering regional innovation, entrepreneurship, and growth through public procurement. *Small Business Economics*, 58, 1205–1222.
 8. Storz, C., Brink, T., & Zou, N. (2022). Innovation in emerging economies: How do university-industry linkages and public procurement matter to small businesses? *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 39, 1439–1480.
 9. Wang, C., Cao, F., & Yang, J. (2021). Whole-process performance management of government procurement: a quantitative analysis of 58 policy texts. *SN Business & Economics*, 1, 163.
 10. Tas, B. K. O. (2020). Effect of public procurement regulation on competition and cost-effectiveness. *Journal of Regulatory Economics*, 58, 59–77.
 11. Changalima, I. A., Ismail, I. J., & Mchopa, A. D. (2021). A review of the forms, rationale, and challenges of supplier development in public procurement: lessons for public buyers in Tanzania. *Future Business Journal*, 7, 63.
 12. Pisareva, O. M., Suyazova, S. A., & Denisova, A. I. (2021). Comparative Analysis of Success Factors for Implementing Public Digital Procurement Platforms: Domestic and World Experience. In: Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) "Smart Technologies" for Society, State, and Economy. ISC 2020. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 155. Springer, Cham.
 13. Borisova, V. V., Lysochenko, A. A., Vorobyev, G. A., Pavlenko, I. I., & Avsharov, A. G. (2021). Digital Technologies in Public Procurement Logistics. In: Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) *Modern Global Economic System: Evolutional Development vs. Revolutionary*

- Leap. ISC 2019. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol. 198. Springer, Cham.
14. Konov, A., Begtin, I., & Gorbacheva, N. 2019. System of Public Procurement in Russia: Competition vs. Quality? Moscow, CPUR; Anticorruption Center of the National Research University Higher School of Economics, 64 p.
15. Federal Law "On the contractual system in the sphere of procurement of goods, works, services to ensure state and municipal needs" from 05.04.2013 # 44-FZ. 2013, No. 14, Art. 1652
16. Garin, A. V., Lomakin, M. I., Dokukin, A. V., Niyazova, Y. M., & Zlydnev, M. I. (2021). Reputational standards for the qualification of suppliers in the emergency situation. *Standards and quality*, 12, 40–43.
17. Alekseev, S. L., & Gordeev, S. G. (2022). Features of risk management of public procurement in the context of threats to national security. *Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 146 (9), 160–163. DOI: 10.34925/EIP.2022.146.9.028
18. Gordeev, S. G. (2022). Problems of increasing the efficiency of public procurement procedures in the context of threats to national security. *Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 146 (9), 234–237. DOI 10.34925/EIP.2022.146.9.044
19. Alekseev, S. L., Gordeev, S. G., & Darenkov A. A. [et al.]. (2022). Key defects of the concept of social control in the legal definition of regional economy. *Management Accounting*, 12-1, 165–175. DOI: 10.25806/uu12-12022165-175

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Sergey L. Alekseev (Russia, Kazan) – Associate Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Professor of the Department of Economics, Accounting and Social and Humanities Sciences. Vice Rector. Honored Lawyer of the Republic of Tatarstan. Tatar Institute for Retraining of Agribusiness Personnel. E-mail: tany_1313@mail.ru. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6765-8347

Sergey G. Gordeev (Russia, Kazan) – Postgraduate student at the Department of Economics, Accounting and Social and Human Sciences. Tatar Institute for Retraining of Agribusiness Personnel. E-mail: sg.gordeev@mail.ru. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1895-9848

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2022/12/01/alekseev/>

Received: Jun 30, 2022 | **Accepted:** Sep 12, 2022 | **Published:** Dec 1, 2022

Editor: Eduard A. Sosnin. Dr. Sci. (Phys.-Math.). National Research Tomsk State University, RUSSIA

Copyright: © 2022 Alekseev, S., Gordeev, S. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.